

Use of Lung and Liver Computer Modeling in Preclinical Practice

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1. Introduction

Investigation of organs – functionality of healthy organs together with diseased is improved these days. Beside *in vitro* and *in vivo* examination, there is a new branch of organ observation in lab conditions – organ-on-a-chip devices. These devices produce more physiological environment to the tissue, in comparison to *in vitro* experiments and they are not invasive as *in vivo* examination is. Experimental conditions are significantly improved in that way. Numerical models and computer simulations are significant part of research in medicine. The purpose of these *in silico* models is to give more detailed response analysis for different setting of input parameters and also to reduce number of experiments on animals, speed up preclinical trials and reduce time and costs.

Epithelial lung cells (A549, Calu-3) can be used to form functional barrier of lung epithelial tissue in organ-on-a-chip devices [1]. The second component of lung-on-a-chip device is vascular component – endothelial tissue representing blood vessel with blood and monocyte cells circulation. As a vascular component, we have worked on development of bioreactor containing circulating blood and monocyte cells.

Human hepatic cell lines (being cancer-derived or immortalized hepatocytes), can be effectively cultured and used in different purposes. Widely used hepatic cell lines are HepG2, Huh7, Hep3B, and SK-Hep-1, derived from hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC), and HepaRG, which is an HCC cell line (includes both hepatocytes and biliary-like cells) [1]. The main use of liver cell lines in *in vitro* research is in the studies of cancer development and therapy [2]. However, computer liver models are limited and primarily developed in order to analyse toxicity of drug metabolites [1].

Particularly for hepatocytes (liver cells), formation of spheroidal multicellular aggregates has been of great interest, as it has been shown to improve cell viability and functionality in comparison to traditional monolayer culture techniques. In order to obtain spheroids, freshly isolated cells are seeded in culture wells coated with ECM and bathed in a culture medium. If the substrate is

adequate, cells aggregate after a certain period of time. Afterwards, aggregates detach themselves from the surface of the ECM and reorganize to form multicellular spheroids [3]. The process is very interesting to simulate in order to reduce number of experiments and optimize conditions necessary to form the aggregates [4].

As a result, this abstract presents simplified models of bioreactor and hepatocyte cell aggregation, as well as initial web application developed for the end-users.

2. Methods

2.1 Simulations of bioreactor

The first model is model of bioreactor filled with fluid and monocyte cells. This model is solved numerically using finite element method and in-house solver PAK. As it is can be used as a component for lung-on-a-chip model, we have simulated vascular component of the system (blood vessel through which the blood and monocyte cells circulate). There is a special interest in monocyte cells due to simulation of inflammation process (one of the future outputs of the model).

2.2 Simulations with liver cells

The second developed model is model concerning aggregation of hepatic liver cells. Model includes description of early stages of cell aggregation process, when the cell clusters form on the surface of the extracellular matrix (ECM) layer on which they are seeded. The equations include interactions between the hepatic cells and the viscoelastic ECM layer. We start from principles of mass and momentum balance equations for cells, culture medium, and ECM. After non-dimensionalization, model is reduced to a system of four coupled partial differential equations. Inputs to the model are initial seeding density function, length of domain of interest, aggregation timescale and different material characteristics for ECM and cells. Predicted outputs are velocity of the cells, cell volume fraction, and cell density as a function of time.

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3. Results and discussion

Web application was developed for these two models. On the platform, the end-user can choose to select several input parameters in order to visualize specific output results.

For the bioreactor model, end user can tune several parameters – fluid velocity at inlet, density and dynamic viscosity of the fluid and number of monocyte cells as well as their diffusion coefficient (Figure 1 - left). Outputs from the bioreactor model, filled with fluid including monocyte cells, are fluid velocity and distribution (stream lines), pressure of the fluid, shear stress on the bioreactor, velocity of the monocyte cells (Figure 1 - right) and their pathways. Results obtained in PAK solver [5] are comparable with the one obtained in commercial software ANSYS.

Figure 1: Input parameters of simulation, web application (left); Obtained monocyte velocity vectors (right).

For the hepatocyte cell aggregation model, web application includes setting up the aforementioned parameters (Figure 2 - left side), where the user can see the acceptable defined ranges for input parameters and start a new calculation. Old results can be loaded, as well as the parameters from that calculation (Figure 2 – upper right corner). Results from the calculation are available through a series of graphs. Numerous tool tips are available (starting from default recommended input parameters to explanations on how to interpret the results).

Figure 2: User-friendly interface for hepatocyte cell aggregation model

4. Conclusions

In silico models take more and more space in medical research. They can provide faster response of the observed system, reduce time and costs and number of experiments. Numerical organ models can be very useful for doctors, especially for clinicians. *In silico* models can be part of preclinical and clinical trials or used in diagnosis and personalized medicine sector. There are not many mathematical and numerical lung and liver models that can be found in literature. Thus, this is emerging field of investigation. Our models are simplified models related to lung and liver, but yet they are good starting point in development of *in silico* models for these organs. Besides, for these models, user-friendly web application is created, which can be used by researchers or clinicians.

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6. References

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